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An Analysis of The First Language Acquisition: A Three Years Girl and A Three Years Boy

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Abstract

Language acquisition is a natural process of children in getting language from zero ability become fluency in using language. This research focused on first language acquisition analysis and factors that influence first language (L1) acquisition. It conducted with descriptive qualitative method. The subject of this research is two children in three years old, which is consist of one girl and one boy. The writer took her boy and nephew as the research subject. Observation and documentation in video recording form is technique that used in collecting the data. After the data have been collected and analyzed, it found out (1) Language development of three years girl is faster than three years boy, (2) there are internal factor that affecting first language acquisition of children, and (3) there are external factors that affecting first language acquisition.

Keywords: First Language Acquisition, Internal Factors, External Factors

1. INTRODUCTION

As a natural process, every human have ability in acquiring their first language (L1) when they was born. It is because human have very important tool that given by God, which called as Language Acquisition Device (LAD). Chomsky in Da Cruz (2015:6) said that children's ability to learn language is due to a genetically programmed organ that is located in the brain. It is means that since birth, human have an innate tool for acquiring the language.

Language that is firstly received by the children since they was born called as their first language. First language also often called as mother tongue. Mother tongue or first language (L1) is received by child from interaction with her/his family and environment around the child. Several studies showed that children received their first language (L1) from some things, such as; questions that often asked by the child, verbal and non-verbal responded, and interaction.

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In the next development of language, every child has ability in increasing their vocabularies independently. It is showed from their capability in composing a good sentence for making a good communication. When children interact with the adult people, they learn about the structure of the word and sentence. If there is someone who said something in wrong sentence, the children not only imitate the sentence, but also they learn about the structure. That is a part of children language development.

Basically there are four phases in children language development according to Nababan (1988). They are babbling in the first phase, the next phase is one word one phrase, the next phase is three words one phrase, and the last is telegram. Every child has different development in acquiring their first language (L1), although they are in the same age. Because there a lot of factors that affecting it. The first language acquisition is unique problem that should be researchers' concern. So, the writer is really excited to analyze that problem.

First Language Acquisition

Gentner & Namy (2006: 1) stated, "Language acquisition is one of humankind's most impressive cognitive feats. A 6-month-old can do little more than babble, but by 2 or 3 years of age, children show generative knowledge of the patterns of their language—that is, they can extend the words they hear to new situations, and they can use grammatical constructions in new contexts". Every child has capability in acquiring language from his environment. They pass though several phases in acquiring the language. Since they were born until grow up. In the first phase, children get their first language for the first time without being taught the grammar by their parents. They acquire their first language naturally. It is called as first language acquisition.

First language acquisition that is language that acquire by the children for the first time, usually called as a mother tongue. First language acquire by the children unaware way (natural) in their family environment. Every child in their environment acquires their first language efficiently. In the other word, they can mastery the language naturally without learning in school. Krashen (2006:121) said that the product of a subconscious process very similar to the process children undergo when they acquire their first language. It is clear that children can master their first language (L1) or mother tongue naturally.

Stages in First Language Acquisition

First language is acquired through six phases/stages. It is because when the human was born, they do not have grammatical complete with the rules about their first language in their brain. They are namely:

- Pre-talking stage / Cooing (0-6 months)
According to Bolinger (2002:283) pre-talking stage or cooing is the vowel-like sound responding to human sounds more definitely, turns head, eyes seem to search for speaker occasionally some chuckling sounds. For example, the sounds of "oh", "uh", and "ah".

- Babbling stage (6-8 months)
Babbling is the sounds which infants produce as consonant-vowel combinations, Steinberg (2003:147). The sounds are such as [ma-ma-ma] or [da-da-da] and [ba-ba-ba] or [na-na-na].
- Holophrastic stage (9-18 months)
Fromkin (1983:328) defined holophrastic from holo “complete” or “undivided” plus phrase “phrase” or “sentence”. So holophrastic is the children’s first single word which represent to a sentence.
- The three-word stage (18-24 months)
Fromkin (1983:329) states that children begin to form actual three-word sentences, with the relations between the three words showing definite syntactic and semantic relations and the intonation contour of the three words extending over the whole utterance rather than being separated by a pause between the three words.
- Telegraphic stage (24-30 months)
Fromkin (1983:330) states that telegraphic is merely a descriptive term because the child does not deliberately leave out the non-content words, as does an adult sending a telegram.
- Later multiword stage (30+months)
According to Bolinger (2002:283) at this stage is fastest increase in vocabulary with many new additions every day; no babbling at all; utterances have communicative intent.

There are stages in first language acquisition in table form;

Tabel 1. Mathew Saxton theory

Age (Months)	Linguistics Milestone
0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognition and preference of mother’s voice (even from the inside the womb!) ▪ Ability to distinguish phonemes ▪ Can distinguish own language from foreign language
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Child can recognise own name ▪ Child is sensitive to word order
7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Early babbling is seen ▪ Starts to understand first words (e.g. Mummy)
12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Jargoning (when babbling becomes more specified to the child’s mother tongue: stress and intonation patterns are recognizable) ▪ First words produced
18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Understand around 50 words ▪ Produce two-words utterance
24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multi words utterance produced with basic grammatical

	features
60	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 6000 words capacity▪ Ability to produce complex sentences has been gained, with full comprehension

Every child passed every stage above in acquiring their first language. However, every child has different language development. The different often appear from 12 months until 60 months. It is proved from the previous studies about first language acquisition.

Theories of First Language Acquisition

1. Behaviorism theory: it focuses toward language behavior that can observe directly. There is a relation between stimulus and response.
2. Nativism theory: Chomsky said that language behavior is something genetic, universal, and environment gives a little impact.
3. Cognitivist theory: Piaget said that language is comes from cognitive development
4. Interactionism theory: Howard Gardner said that environment affect the first language acquisition

Internal Factor that affecting First Language Acquisition

1. Age

Chronological age affects language acquisition of children, especially their mother tongue. There are six stages that they passed in acquiring the first language. They are pre-talking stage / Cooing (0-6 months), babbling stage (6-8 months), holophrastic stage (9-18 months), the three-word stage (18-24 months), telegraphic stage (24-30 months), and later multiword stage (30+months)

2. Gender

Several studies found that gender factor affect the language development of children. It found that language development of girl is faster than boy. It can be shown if the girl mastery more vocabularies and long sentences in doing communication. But this difference appears to children in golden ages (0-5 years old). More than 5 years there is no more difference between girl and boy in their language development.

External Factor that affecting First Language Acquisition

Environment

Howard Gardner said that environment have important function toward first language acquisition of children. It is because their mother tongue they get from their family environment. Language environment is everything around the learners, both audible and visible. In general, language environment can be divided into three, namely (1) a formal environment or artificial that is found in the learning process; (2) natural environment, which is found in the life of society (Krashen, 1982: 40)

1. Economic

Economic is external factor that affects children in acquiring their first language. If the children live in the progressive economic, it affects the children found the result of progressive economic itself, for example, mall, sophisticated playground, and etc. ini.

2. METODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

This study was case-study on the first language acquisition. The participant of this study are three children in same age (3 years old), in different gender. A three years girl named Fatimah Azahra Pradana (participant1). She lives with a big family, which include of mother, father, grandmother, grandfather, three aunties, and one uncle. The second participant is a three years boy. His name is Muhammad Rayhan Alfathan (Participant2). He lives with her mother and father.

There were observation and documentation (video tapping) as technique in collecting the data. Finally, the data that have been collected will be analyzed and described.

3. RESEARCH FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Research Finding

First Language Acquisition Analysis

The writer observed the language skills of the participants. The writer was observed for 6 months. Here is some conversation conducted by the three years girl as participant1 observed in daily life. Hasil dan pembahasan berisi hasil-hasil temuan penelitian dan pembahasannya. Tuliskan temuan-temuan yang diperoleh dari hasil-hasil penelitian yang telah dilakukan dan harus ditunjang oleh data-data yang memadai. Hasil-hasil penelitian dan temuan harus bisa menjawab pertanyaan atau hipotesis penelitian di bagian pendahuluan.

Tabel dan Gambar langsung masuk ke dalam bagian naskah. Contoh dapat dilihat sebagai berikut.

Mother	: “ayo bobo nak!”
Fatim	: “Ndak mami, Fatim mau main”.
Mother	: “bobo dulu, nanti mami ajak jalan-jalan ke pantai”
Fatim	: “Iya bobo tapi nonton hp ya”
Mother	: “hp nya mati lowbet”
Fatim	: “Yobet mi?”
<i>(conversation on September 26th 2018)</i>	

From the conversation above, it showed that the participant1 has many vocabularies and can compose sentence. Beside that there is the communicative between her and

her mother. All the word also can say in clear way, except the word “lowbet”, she said “yobet”.

Mother : “hp nya mati lowbet”
Fatim : “Yobet mi?”

If we concern to the phonological development of the participant1, it looked sounds in order to pronounce words that produce by the participant1 is clear. Although there is sound [L] is incorrect. She said [Y]. So, the word lowbet become yobet. Further, the participant1 has been able to pronounce most of the vocabularies or words in Indonesia clearly.

Another conversation that occurred toward P1 with her grandfather is showed below;

Grandfather : “Fatim, jangan begitu atuh nanti mati kucingnya”
Fatim : “Apa lho tetek ini, fatim sayang sayang kok lingling”
Grandfather : “Nda begitu kalo di sayang”
Fatim : “Tetek jangan gitu atuh, jangan mayah”
(conversation on October 7th 2018)

A vocabulary of the participant1 also depends on her first language acquisition. She lives in big family with Sunda culture as their background, so Sunda’s dialect and vocabularies affects her language acquisition.

Fatim : “Tetek jangan gitu atuh, jangan mayah”

The word atuh is dialect from Sunda. It always appears when the family members talk each other. Then finally, the participant1 also always use that word in her language.

Furthermore, here is some conversation conducted by the three years boy as participant2 observed in daily life. The conversation occurred between participant2 with his mother. He invited his mother for making him milk. Here is the short conversation that occurred between them;

Ray : “Mamah bitin cucu”
Mother : “Ok. Pake botol yang ini ya” (showed the pink bottle)
Ray : “No mamah. Blue”
Mother : “Yang ini”
Ray : “Yes Yes”
(conversation on September 26th 2018)

Participant2 said some words in Indonesia still in unclear pronunciation. For example the word “bitin” is actually come from the word “bikin”. The next, the word “susu”, but the participant2 said it by “cucu”.

Ray : “Mamah *bitin cucu*”

In the other words, the phonological development of participant1 especially in Indonesia language is unclear. He pronounce the letter [k] with the sound [t]. He also pronounce letter [s] by the sound [c].

The unique fact is he has a lot of vocabularies in English. Different with Indonesia vocabularies, he can pronounce words in English clearly, such as and “blue”, “yes”, and “no”. Another conversation from the participant2 as below;

Ray : “Pah, one pah” (invited his father for point out the picture of number 1-10)
Father : “Mas Ray saja sendiri yang tunjuk”
Ray : “Ayo pah mamun, diri mas cey one”
Father : “oke” (point to the number from 1-10)
Ray : “*one, three, three, four, five, six, seven (he said seven in unclear pronounce), eight, nine, ten.*”
Father : “Yeyy, pinternya anak sholeh”
Ray : “*Anyi pah. Head shoulder knees and toes. Ini nose mah, ini mouth*” (he said the words in the correct pronunciation)
(*conversation on October 12nd 2018*)

From conversation above, it showed that participant2 have English and Indonesia as his first language acquisition. He can say a lot of vocabularies in English clearly. For example, he can say the number one to ten (1-10) in a right way, except number seven. Different with Indonesia language, there a lot of word in Indonesia that he said in unclear pronounce. For example the word “bangun”, he said it by “mamun”. The other word is “diri”. He said “diri” for invited his father for stand up (berdiri).

Internal Factors of First Language Acquisition Analysis

1. Chronological Age

Chronological age affects language acquisition of children, especially their mother tongue. There are six stages that they passed in acquiring the first language. They are pre-talking stage / Cooning (0-6 months), babbling stage (6-8 months), holophrastic stage

(9-18 months), the three-word stage (18-24 months), telegraphic stage (24-30 months), and later multiword stage (30+months).

Both of the research participants passed this stage. There is no different with the participant1 and participant2 in acquiring their first language acquisition in the cooing, babbling, and holophrastic stage. The different showed when they are in the three word stage, and the next stage.

Although they were born in the same date or they are in the same age(three years old), but when the chronological age is in the three words-stage, there were a different language development from both of them.

2. Gender

Several studies found that gender factor affect the language development of children. It found that language development of girl is faster than boy. It can be shown if the girl mastery more vocabularies and long sentences in doing communication. From the observation result, the writer also found the same thing toward her research participants

There were the different in acquiring and developing language between girl and boy. In the other word, gender is one of internal factor that affecting first language acquisition of children. It can be proved from the conversation result that occurred to participant1 (three years girl). She can say a lot of Indonesia vocabularies in right and clear way. Besides that, she also can arrange the words in a sentence that formed a long sentence in a good arrangement. So, the listener can understand about what she said without try to analyze the words one by one.

Different with the participant2 (three years boy), he pronounce the Indonesia vocabulary in unclear way. He is also not good enough to arrange words in sentences yet. So, the listeners should analyze what the words he was said one by one. But the unique thing is the participant2 have good pronunciation if say English vocabularies. A lot of words in English, he can say in right pronunciation.

From the observation in the setting towards research participants, it is clear that gender is one of important factor that can affecting first language acquisition of the children, although they are in the same age.

3. Interest

Every child is interested in different things, include in acquire their language. The observation result is became the proof. The participant2 (three years boy) has a lot of vocabularies in English language. He also can pronounce the English words better than Indonesia word. It is because he really excited with the English language. When he watched sing or cartoon movie in the YouTube, he invited her mom for change the program if the content not used English. Different if the YouTube content is using English, he focused to pay attention and sometimes he also repeats the words while watching. Finally he can pronounce well a lot of English vocabularies, such as colours,

animals, part of body, numbers, the name of kinds of ghost in Halloween, and etc. He also mixes the English language and Indonesia when speaking. It was not happening to participant1 (three years girl). She excited to sing a song in Indonesia language. She also often watched the You Tube which is the content use Indonesia language. From the observation toward the two participants, it can be said that interest is one of internal factor that influence children language acquisition.

External Factors of First Language Acquisition Analysis

1. Environment

Howard Gardner said that environment have important function toward first language acquisition of children. It is because their mother tongue they get from their family environment. This statement is appropriate with the research result. The writer found that environment, especially family environment give big effect toward first language acquisition of children.

It can be shown from participant1. Participant1 lives with her big family (mother, father, grandmother, grandfather, aunties, and uncle), automatically a lot of vocabularies that she received when doing interaction with her family members. When she interacts with her mother, she gets new vocabularies that possible it will different if she interacts with other family members. It makes her get lots of vocabularies. Besides that, language ability also affect the frequency of interacts/ practices the language with the others. A big family that she has can make her always practice her language.

Different fact is occurred to the participant2. Participant2 only live with her mother and father. In the workday, his father goes to office and back home in the evening. So automatically, he only has mother as his friend to speaks. It is affect his first language acquisition. But the unique thing is participant2 has capability in using English vocabularies. He says Indonesian vocabularies in unclear way, but he can pronounce English vocabularies well. It is happened because his mother is English lecture, so when his mother come to teach, the participant2 always followed his mother in the classroom.

For that, it is really clear that environment is the most important thing that affecting first language acquisition of children. So, if the parents want their children have a lot of vocabularies and various vocabularies, let's make a good family environment. Family is environment that affects the children for the first time.

2. Economic

Economic is external factor that affects children in acquiring their first language. If the children live in the progressive economic, it affects the children found the result of progressive economic itself, for example, mall, sophisticated playground, and technology. One kinds of technology that affects first language acquisition of children is gadget.

From the observation, the writer found that beside environment, gadget as a progress economic result has important influenced toward their language acquisition. For example is the participant2. He always watches the videos in youtube. Almost the videos are in English language, such as learning numbers, colours, kinds of cars, sing a song, and others. So finally he can say English vocabularies in right pronunciation without her parents' teach. So, the writer concludes that the economy of children environment affects their first language acquisition.

DISCUSSION

From the analyzing, the writer showed that the finding of this research is there were the different of first language acquisition and language development between three years girl and three years boy. It is proved by the capability of participant1 (three years girl) who can say a lot Indonesia vocabularies in right pronunciation. She also can arrange the words in a good sentence, although there were a little incorrect sound, but overall it is good. Different with the participant2 (three years boy) who acquire three languages as his first language acquisition. It is because his parent speaks with him by using Indonesia and English. He can pronounce English words well, but not with Indonesia vocabularies. There a lot of word in Indonesia that he said in unclear pronounce. For example the word "bangun", he said it by "mamun". The other word is "diri". He said "diri" for invited his father for stand up (berdiri). Although the participant2 acquire three languages as his first language, but in language development three years girls is faster than three years boy.

This research also found that there two factors that affecting first language acquisition of children, namely internal factors and external factors. Internal factors consist of age, gender, and interest. In age factor it showed that there is no different with the participant1 and participant2 in acquiring their first language acquisition in the cooing, babbling, and holophrastic stage. The different showed when they are in the three word stage, and the next stage. The next is gender. It showed that language development of girl is faster than boy. It can be shown if the girl mastery more vocabularies and long sentences in doing communication. Interest also one of internal factor that affected children language acquisition. It can be proof by the kinds of language that mastery by the participants is different based their interest. The participant2 really excited with the English language. So he interest in watching You Tube that using English language. Finally, when he is speaking, he can pronounce English better than Indonesia.

Furthermore, the external factors consist of environment and economic. From environment factors, we can see that participant1 have a lot of vocabularies and can compose good sentences in speaking. It is because participant1 lives with her big family (mother, father, grandmother, grandfather, aunties, and uncle), automatically a lot of vocabularies that she received when doing interaction with her family members. Different fact is occurred to the participant2. Participat2 only live with her mother and

father. So automatically, he only has three friends to speaks in a family environment. It is affect his first language acquisition. But the unique thing is participant2 has capability in using English vocabularies. He says Indonesian vocabularies in unclear way, but he can pronounce English vocabularies well. It is happened because his mother also usually used English in speaking when talking to him and his father. The last external factor is economy. From this factor it can be shown that gadget as a progress economic result has important influenced toward children's' language acquisition. For example is the participant2. He always watches the videos in YouTube. Almost the videos are in English language, such as learning numbers, colors, kinds of cars, sing a song, and others. So finally he can say English vocabularies in right pronunciations without her parents' teach. So, it can be concluded that both of the internal factors and external factors are really influential toward first language acquisition of children.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the description of the study result, I can conclude the result in four points as below:

1. Language acquisition and language development of three years girl is different with the three years boy. Three years girl is faster than three years boy.
2. Children can acquire more than one language as their first language acquisition.
3. There are internal factor that affecting first language acquisition of children, namely chronological age, gender, and interest.
4. There external factors that affecting first language acquisition, namely environment and economy..

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